

Semitheoretical INDO Calculation of Activation Energy of Base Hydrolyses of Esters in Solution. Part-II : Substituted and Unsubstituted Ethyl Cinnamates and Ethyl Benzoates in Mixed Aqueous Media

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The INDO SCF MO based approach for calculation of activation energy of hydrolysis of a model ester, ethyl formate, in aqueous medium as developed in Part I serves as a foothold leading to the technique of calculation of activation energies of hydrolyses of unsubstituted and substituted cinnamate and benzoate esters in water. These hypothetical aqueous medium values and the corresponding relations are further developed for incorporation of the effect of variation of dielectric constant of the medium. The activation energies in organo-aqueous binaries thus emerge as a natural sequence of the calculation technique. The technique also takes into consideration the contribution of π -delocalisation energy to activation energies. Accord with experimental values is encouraging.

In a previous communication (Part I)¹, we have developed a method, based on Born Haber type of cycle, INDO computation and evaluation of solvation energy, for calculating the activation energy (15.78 kcal/mole) for the base hydrolysis of a model ester in aqueous medium. This method and the model ester value will serve as the springboard for further development of the process for calculation of the energy of activation in the hydrolyses of other substituted and unsubstituted esters.

Let us consider how we can theoretically arrive at the activation energy values of the base hydrolyses of ethyl esters of cinnamic and substituted cinnamic acids for which there exist experimental data^{2,3} in different dielectric media. The technique is the evolution of a correlation between the model ester value and the activation energy values of hydrolyses in purely aqueous medium of the substituted and unsubstituted ethyl cinnamates. Finally, there is set up a correlation between activation energy values for hydrolyses in aqueous medium with those in organo-aqueous binaries of different dielectric constant. Keeping in view the Born Haber type of cycle of part I of this series¹ and representing the activation energy of the model ester in water by $\Delta H_{(M)/w}^\ddagger$, one can write, following Dewar⁴,

$$\Delta H_{(M)/w}^\ddagger = \underbrace{\Delta E(C_{sp^2} \rightarrow C_{sp^3}) + \Delta E(\text{>C=O} \rightarrow \text{>C<O}^-) + E(\text{>C<OH}) - E_{OH^-}}_{\text{gas phase}} + \Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(M) + \Delta H_{\text{Hydrn.}}(M) = A + \Delta H_{\text{Hydrn.}}(M) + \Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(M) \quad \dots (1)$$

where,

$\Delta E(C_{sp^2} \rightarrow C_{sp^3})$ = Difference in energy per mole due to switchover of an sp^2 C-atom of the model ester to roughly sp^3 state in the gas phase 'model ester-OH⁻ adduct' i.e., 'the precursor'.

$\Delta E(\text{>C=O} \rightarrow \text{>C<O}^-)$ = Difference in bond energy per mole of a nearly tetrahedral (>C<O⁻) arrangement of the gas phase 'ester-OH⁻ adduct' and of the carbonyl bond of the gas phase model ester.

$E(\text{>C<OH})$ = Bond energy per mole of the C-OH bond of the gas phase 'ester-OH⁻ adduct'.

E_{OH^-} = Binding energy per mole of the gas phase OH⁻ ion.

$\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(M)$ = Difference in the delocalisation energy per mole of the 'model ester-OH⁻ adduct' and of the model ester in the gas phase.

$\Delta H_{\text{Hydrn.}}(M)$ = Hydration energy per mole of the gas phase 'ester-OH⁻ adduct' + the dehydration energies of both the model ester and the OH⁻ ion originally present in solution.

Similarly, $\Delta H_{(C)/w}^\ddagger$, the activation energy for hydrolysis of ethyl cinnamate in water, can be written as :

$$\Delta H_{(C)/w}^\ddagger = A + \Delta H_{\text{Hydrn.}}(C) + \Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(C) \quad \dots (2)$$

where, $\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(\text{C})$ = difference in the delocalisation energies of the gas phase 'ethyl cinnamate-OH⁻ adduct' and of the gas phase ethyl cinnamate.

From (1) and (2) we get,

$$\Delta H_{(\text{C})/w}^{\ddagger} = \Delta H_{(\text{M})/w}^{\ddagger} + [\Delta H_{\text{Hydrn.}}(\text{C}) - \Delta H_{\text{Hydrn.}}(\text{M})] + \Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(\text{C}) - \Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(\text{M}) \quad \dots (3)$$

The terms within parenthesis in equation (3) lead to a very low value, since these represent the difference between very similar terms of hydration energy, and thus can be neglected. Since $\Delta H_{(\text{M})/w}^{\ddagger}$ is available theoretically (Part I)², the crux of the problem, as presented by equation (3), now reduces to a brace of calculations of differences in delocalisation energies, viz., $\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(\text{C})$ and $\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(\text{M})$.

Incidentally, it may be noted, that correlations, analogous to equation (3), between $\Delta H_{(\text{M})/w}^{\ddagger}$ and the activation energies of hydrolyses of different ethyl cinnamates in water can also be built up. These are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta H_{(p\text{-OMeC})/w}^{\ddagger} &= \Delta H_{(\text{M})/w}^{\ddagger} + \Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(p\text{-OMeC}) - \Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(\text{M}) \\ \Delta H_{(p\text{-MeC})/w}^{\ddagger} &= \Delta H_{(\text{M})/w}^{\ddagger} + \Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(p\text{-MeC}) - \Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(\text{M}) \\ \Delta H_{(m\text{-MeC})/w}^{\ddagger} &= \Delta H_{(\text{M})/w}^{\ddagger} + \Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(m\text{-MeC}) - \Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(\text{M}) \end{aligned} \right\} \dots (3a)$$

where the abbreviations *p*-OMeC, *p*-MeC, *m*-MeC stand for ethyl *p*-methoxy, *p*-methyl and *m*-methyl cinnamates, respectively.

Since in an all valence shell treatment⁵ involving σ and π electrons as in INDO method, the π -delocalisation energy does not come out as a distinguishable component of the total evaluated energy, one has to fall back upon one of the available methods⁶⁻⁸ for calculation of $\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}$. Since this π -energy involvement is likely to affect the activation energy in only a peripheral manner as a substituent effect, we adopt the simple Hückel method involving heteroatom parameters⁹ to evaluate the $\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}$ terms in equations (3) and (3a). The results are presented in Table 1.

The $\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}$, available from Table 1 in the garb of β parameters, can be meaningfully used only after fixing the magnitude of β_0 . The π -bond literature is replete with many dissenting views on the possible magnitudes of β_0 . A critical sum up by Streitwieser⁹ permits the use of -17 kcal/mole to -20 kcal/mole for β in benzenoid π -systems. For non-benzenoid systems, the values are widely different.

Since our esters consist of mostly benzenoid systems and since the heteroatom parameters used are calibrated on that basis, we use $\beta_0 = -18$ kcal/mole. Thus we are able to calculate, with the help of equations (3) and (3a), the activation energies for the four cinnamates in water. These are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—HEATS OF ACTIVATION OF BASE HYDROLYSES OF DIFFERENT CINNAMATE ESTERS IN WATER ($D_w=78.5$)

Ester (X)	Heat of activation of 'model ester' $\Delta H_{(\text{M})/w}^{\ddagger}$ (kcal/mole)	$\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(\text{X}) - \Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(\text{M})$ (kcal/mole)	Heat of activation of cinnamate ester $\Delta H_{(\text{X})/w}^{\ddagger}$ (kcal/mole)
Ethyl cinnamate (C)	15.78	7.18	22.96
Ethyl <i>p</i> -methoxy cinnamate (<i>p</i> -OMeC)	"	7.33	23.11
Ethyl <i>p</i> -methyl cinnamate (<i>p</i> -MeC)	"	7.29	23.07
Ethyl <i>m</i> -methyl cinnamate (<i>m</i> -MeC)	"	7.18	22.96

Activation energies of base hydrolyses of cinnamates in mixed aqueous medium. Effect of dielectric†

The heats of activation of the different cinnamate esters recorded in Table 2 refer to calculated values in aqueous medium with dielectric constant 78.5. The fact that the cinnamate esters do not appreciably dissolve in pure water and thus do not permit an experimental determination of their activation heats of hydrolysis in aqueous medium, does not invalidate the calculated results.

From the values of the heat of activation $\Delta H_{(\text{X})/w}^{\ddagger}$ of the different cinnamate esters (X) in pure water obtained in the previous section, $\Delta H_{(\text{X})/m}^{\ddagger}$, i.e. the corresponding values in an organoaqueous medium (*m*) of a given dielectric constant D_m can be calculated. The realisation of this latter correlation is possible subject to certain conditions being satisfied. These are:

- (i) In organoaqueous medium (*m*), the primary solvation of the ester, the OH⁻ ion and also of the 'ester-OH⁻ adduct' (precursor) is due to the water molecules only, i.e., the solvated species is compositionally and dimensionally the same as in pure aqueous medium.

TABLE 1—DELOCALISATION ENERGIES OF ESTERS AND 'ESTER-HYDROXYL ION ADDUCTS'

System	Total π -energy	Estimated localised π -energy	$E_{\text{Deloc.}}$	$\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}$
Ethyl formate (Model)	$4\alpha_0 + 7.577\beta_0$	$4\alpha_0 + 7.236\beta_0$	$0.341\beta_0$	$\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(\text{M})$ = $-0.341\beta_0$
Ethyl formate-OH ⁻ adduct	0	0	0	
Ethyl cinnamate	$12\alpha_0 + 18.508\beta_0$	$12\alpha_0 + 15.236\beta_0$	$3.272\beta_0$	$\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(\text{C})$ = $-0.74\beta_0$
Ethyl cinnamate-OH ⁻ adduct	$8\alpha_0 + 10.532\beta_0$	$8\alpha_0 + 8\beta_0$	$2.532\beta_0$	
Ethyl <i>p</i> -methoxy cinnamate	$14\alpha_0 + 22.715\beta_0$	$14\alpha_0 + 19.236\beta_0$	$3.479\beta_0$	$\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(p\text{-OMeC})$ = $-0.748\beta_0$
Ethyl <i>p</i> -methoxy cinnamate-OH ⁻ adduct	$10\alpha_0 + 14.781\beta_0$	$10\alpha_0 + 12\beta_0$	$2.781\beta_0$	
Ethyl <i>p</i> -methyl cinnamate	$14\alpha_0 + 22.666\beta_0$	$14\alpha_0 + 19.236\beta_0$	$3.43\beta_0$	$\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(p\text{-MeC})$ = $-0.746\beta_0$
Ethyl <i>p</i> -methyl cinnamate-OH ⁻ adduct	$10\alpha_0 + 14.684\beta_0$	$10\alpha_0 + 12\beta_0$	$2.684\beta_0$	
Ethyl <i>m</i> -methyl cinnamate	$14\alpha_0 + 22.659\beta_0$	$14\alpha_0 + 19.236\beta_0$	$3.423\beta_0$	$\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(m\text{-MeC})$ = $-0.74\beta_0$
Ethyl <i>m</i> -methyl cinnamate-OH ⁻ adduct	$10\alpha_0 + 14.683\beta_0$	$10\alpha_0 + 12\beta_0$	$2.683\beta_0$	

TABLE 3—HEATS OF ACTIVATION OF THE BASE HYDROLYSES OF DIFFERENT CINNAMATE ESTERS IN DIFFERENT ORGANO-AQUEOUS MEDIA $D_w=78.5$

Ester (X)	D.C. of the medium D_m	$\Delta H_{(X)/w}^\ddagger$ (k cal/mole)	$N \left(\sum_i \frac{q_i^2}{2R_i} + \sum_{i < j} \frac{q_i q_j}{R_{ij}} \right)$ (k cal/mole)			$\Delta H_{(X)/m}^\ddagger$ (k cal/mole) (Calcd.)	$\Delta H_{(X)/m}^\ddagger$ (k cal/mole) (Exptl.) ^{a,b}
			Model ester	Hydroxyl ion	Precursor		
Ethyl cinnamate	44.4	22.96	19.66	117.55	116.52	22.76	17.44
	41.6					22.73	17.49
	38.7					22.69	16.63
	35.8					22.65	17.39
	32.9					22.59	17.89
	30.0					22.53	19.17
Ethyl <i>p</i> -methoxy cinnamate	27.3	23.11	19.66	117.55	116.52	22.47	18.49
	38.7					22.83	17.00
	35.8					22.79	16.78
	32.9					22.74	17.97
	30.0					22.68	20.41
	27.3					22.61	19.58
Ethyl <i>p</i> -methyl cinnamate	38.7	23.07	19.66	117.55	116.52	22.80	12.57
	35.8					22.75	12.74
	32.9					22.70	13.74
	30.0					22.64	16.10
	27.3					22.57	16.45
	50.0					22.81	11.52
Ethyl <i>m</i> -methyl cinnamate	44.4	22.96	19.66	117.55	116.52	22.76	11.58
	38.7					22.69	13.21
	32.9					22.59	13.16
	30.0					22.53	13.21
	27.3					22.47	13.25
	50.0					22.81	11.52

(ii) Dimensional identity of the solvated species means R_i and R_{ij} values in organo-aqueous medium (m) to be the same as in purely aqueous medium (w).

Referring to equation (1) of part I¹, the activation energies $\Delta H_{(M)/w}^\ddagger$ and $\Delta H_{(M)/m}^\ddagger$ for the hydrolyses of the model ester in water (w) and in organo-aqueous medium (m), respectively, can be expressed as :

$$\Delta H_{(M)/w}^\ddagger = \Delta H_g - \Delta H_{Hydrn.}(ester) - \Delta H_{Hydrn.}(OH^-) + \Delta H_{Hydrn.}(precursor)$$

and

$$\Delta H_{(M)/m}^\ddagger = \Delta H_g - \Delta H_{Solvn.}(ester) - \Delta H_{Solvn.}(OH^-) + \Delta H_{Solvn.}(precursor)$$

Or, remembering equation (3) of Part I¹ and the symbols therein,

$$\begin{aligned} & \Delta H_{(M)/m}^\ddagger - \Delta H_{(M)/w}^\ddagger \\ &= \{ \Delta H_{Hydrn.}(ester) - \Delta H_{Solvn.}(ester) \} \\ &+ \{ \Delta H_{Hydrn.}(OH^-) - \Delta H_{Solvn.}(OH^-) \} \\ &- \{ \Delta H_{Hydrn.}(precursor) - \Delta H_{Solvn.}(precursor) \} \\ &= N \left[\left(\sum_i \frac{q_i^2}{2R_i} + \sum_{i < j} \frac{q_i q_j}{R_{ij}} \right)_{ester} \right. \\ &+ \left. \left(\sum_i \frac{q_i^2}{2R_i} + \sum_{i < j} \frac{q_i q_j}{R_{ij}} \right)_{OH^-} \right. \\ &\left. - \left(\sum_i \frac{q_i^2}{2R_i} + \sum_{i < j} \frac{q_i q_j}{R_{ij}} \right)_{precursor} \right] \left(\frac{1}{D_w} - \frac{1}{D_m} \right) \dots (4) \end{aligned}$$

Following equations (3) and (3a), the activation energies $\Delta H_{(X)/w}^\ddagger$ and $\Delta H_{(X)/m}^\ddagger$ for a cinnamate ester

(X) in water (w) and in a mixed medium (m) can be expressed as :

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Delta H_{(X)/w}^\ddagger &= \Delta H_{(M)/w}^\ddagger + \Delta E_{Deloc.}(X) - \Delta E_{Deloc.}(M) \\ \Delta H_{(X)/m}^\ddagger &= \Delta H_{(M)/m}^\ddagger + \Delta E_{Deloc.}(X) - \Delta E_{Deloc.}(M) \end{aligned} \right\} \dots (5)$$

whence we get,

$$\Delta H_{(X)/m}^\ddagger - \Delta H_{(X)/w}^\ddagger = \Delta H_{(M)/m}^\ddagger - \Delta H_{(M)/w}^\ddagger \dots (6)$$

The R.H.S. of equation (6) being obtainable from equation (4), and $\Delta H_{(X)/w}^\ddagger$ already known from Table 2, $\Delta H_{(X)/m}^\ddagger$ can be calculated for the different cinnamate esters in various dielectrics for ready comparison with experimental values^{2,3}. The results are given in Table 3.

Considering the present state of the semitheoretical calculation of the heats of activation for reactions in solution and the difficulties involved, the calculated results may be considered quite satisfactory. It is important to note that the calculations are rigidly valid under some restricted conditions already stated. The conditions imply that the mixed medium does not involve any solvent structure effect nor any solute-solvent interaction. Moreover, the conditions also demand that the organic solvent molecules do not vie with water molecules for occupation of sites in the primary solvation sheath. These conditions, one or the other, are rather unlikely to be fulfilled in very highly aquated mixed media where structure promotion or demolition may be important¹⁰⁻¹². Also, where a very high percentage of organic component is present in the binary

solvent, will there ensue a competition between these solvent molecules and water molecules for participation in primary solvation. It is, therefore, over a limited zone where the change in the dielectric continuum is the principal governing factor, that the above mode of calculation exhibits its usefulness.

Application to ethyl benzoate systems :

The procedure adopted for calculation of activation energies of hydrolyses of ethyl cinnamates (substituted and unsubstituted) may also be employed for the benzoate series, the experimental data of which have been furnished by Ingold and Nathan¹³. The calculated results appear in Table 4 wherein the last column displays the experimental values for comparison. The accord is encouraging and speaks in favour of the method developed in the foregoing pages.

TABLE 4—ACTIVATION ENERGIES FOR THE BASE HYDROLYSIS OF DIFFERENT ETHYL BENZOATES

Ester (X)	Medium (m)	D _m (25°)	$\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(X)$ $-\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(M)$ (k cal/mole)	$\Delta H_{(X)/m}^{\ddagger}$ (k cal/mole) (Calcd.)	$\Delta H_{(X)/m}^{\ddagger}$ (k cal/mole) (Exptl.) ¹³
Ethyl Benzoate (B)	85% (w/w) aqueous ethanol	30.2	6.25	21.60	17.70
Ethyl <i>p</i> -chloro benzoate (<i>p</i> -ClB)	"	"	6.32	21.67	16.80
Ethyl <i>p</i> -bromo benzoate (<i>p</i> -BrB)	"	"	6.48	21.84	16.80
Ethyl <i>p</i> -methyl benzoate (<i>p</i> -MeB)	"	"	6.44	21.80	18.20
Ethyl <i>p</i> -nitro benzoate (<i>p</i> -NO ₂ B)	"	"	6.03	21.39	14.50

It may be seen from equation (5) that an ester like ethyl propionate, ethyl butyrate and others, which have $\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}$ values the same as $\Delta E_{\text{Deloc.}}(M)$, should have the same heat of activation as the model ester. This is borne out fairly well by experimental values. The small differences observed in practice are perhaps due to $\Delta H_{\text{Hydr.}}$ terms [equation (3)], the differences of which have been neglected in the final derivation.

In conclusion, it may be mentioned that a good deal depends on the semitheoretically calculated value of $\Delta H_{(M)/w}^{\ddagger}$ (Part I). At present, in spite of its INDO SCF molecular orbital background, its value is also dependent upon an empirical factor $\rho'_E \approx 0.45$. A method for a theoretical evaluation of a precise ρ'_E has to be discovered and a search for such a discovery is proceeding in this laboratory at present.

References

1. S. C. RAKSHIT and S. DATTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 456.
2. S. C. RAKSHIT and S. DATTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1104.
3. S. C. RAKSHIT and S. DATTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **17A**, 406.
4. M. J. S. DEWAR, "Molecular Orbital Theory of Organic Chemistry", McGraw Hill Book Company, 1969, p. 289.
5. Topics in Current Chemistry, 22, "σ and π Electrons in Organic Compounds", Springer Verlag, New York, 1971.
6. D. H. LO and M. A. WHITEHEAD, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1968, **46**, 2027, 2041.
7. M. J. S. DEWAR and CARLOS DE LLANO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 789.
8. A. L. H. CHUNG and M. J. S. DEWAR, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1965, **42**, 756.
9. A. STREITWIESER, JR., "Molecular Orbital Theory for Organic Chemists", J. Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1961.
10. E. M. ARNETT in "Physico-Chemical Processes in Mixed Aqueous Solvents", (Ed.), F. FRANKS, Heinemann Educational Books Ltd., London, 1967, p. 105.
11. H. S. FRANK and M. W. EVANS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1945, **13**, 507.
12. D. N. GLEW, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 605.
13. C. K. INGOLD and W. S. NATHAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 222.